

Microalgae Culture Decision Support Tool MCDST *Explorer* version 1.2

ARKdynamics.org

Microalgae Culture Decision Support Tool (MCDST) Explorer version. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18642860>

Please note that the model itself is available at the same DOI location

Operational exclusions and technical information

Microalgal growth always carries with it various risks associated with the mass culturing of microbes that run beyond technical aspects of the culture facility. For this reason, the MCDST can only ever be a '**decision support tool**', with the sole purpose of helping to guide you in your deliberations. For these reasons, the use of the tool carries the following exclusions, which apply to all version of the MCDST:

- The MCDST is intended solely to provide additional insight on operating a real microalgal culture facility.
- The developer, ARKdynamics Ltd, provides no guarantee or other assurance what-so-ever that what the tool describes will come to pass in reality.
- The user bears all responsibility, and any/all financial consequences, of using the MCDST.

The MCDST operates within the *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* application. This application is a long-established product of **Powersim Software AS**. The application is very stable, and we have never encountered any issues with installations and operations across many different Windows PC configurations.

Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit runs the same core software code as the system dynamics simulation software, *Powersim Studio 10*. If you require further technical information on PC system requirements, visit the Powersim web site at:

<https://powersim.com/powersim-studio/>

The *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* application is available as a free download. The download is available in 32 or 64 bit versions, as suits your PC configuration, from:

<https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>

With respect to *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit*, please note the following:

- It is the responsibility of the user to ensure that *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* is satisfactorily installed on their PC.
- The developer of the MCDST, ARKdynamics Ltd, can provide no guarantee that future versions of the *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* application (which is downloaded and installed onto the user's PC from Powersim.com, as detailed above) will function in the same way as the version available at the time of the original installation.

Acquisition of any version of the MCDST provides the user with access only to the functionality of the tool, and not to the model code.

Microalgae Culture Decision Support Tool (MCDST)

Explorer version 1.2

Introduction

The growth of microalgae is affected by many factors. Optimising these to provide the highest rates of production, with the most cost-effective solution, is non-trivial and requires various trade-offs. The *MCDST* is a simulation modelling tool specifically designed to help resolve these challenges.

The *MCDST* can help you decide the configuration of your operations with respect to aspects such as:

- PBR or pond configuration
- Media nutrient composition
- Lighting regimes
- Productivity for biomass vs for specific chemical composition
- Harvesting regimes

The *MCDST* operates on your PC; your data are secure with nothing on the cloud, and no need for real-time internet access.

Developed from over 20yrs experience of modelling microalgal physiology, exploiting system dynamics approaches, supporting extensive peer-reviewed publication, these new tools provide an extensive range of input and output options to configure the decision support tool in line with the culture system, and the physiology of the organism of interest.

The *MCDST Explorer* provides you with a zero-cost introduction to the capabilities of more comprehensive *MCDST* variants.

Limitations of the *MCDST Explorer v1.2*

The *MCDST Explorer* version provides a simple interface, allowing the user to quickly conduct simple what-if tests.

In the *MCDST Explorer* version, the user configures the system by selecting from a limited range of pre-defined options. Simulation output is provided using time-graphs.

For more comprehensive and scenario-specific investigations, more advanced versions of the *MCDST* are available. For advanced versions, the interface uses sliders, direct data entry, or control data can be imported from a spreadsheet. Simulation output may also be output to a spreadsheet. These versions can also provide greater scenario descriptions, for example with geolocated illumination (based on latitude and date), detailed description of nutrients, chemostat/turbidostat functionality, pH. Also available is a detailed configuration of the algal physiology, including variable C:N:P:Si:Fe:Chl, temperature and pH linkage to growth, photoacclimation and photodamage, toxin, allelopath, etc.. Bespoke systems, including coupling to a comprehensive finance model, can be developed. Please visit our web site at www.ARKdynamics.org or email us at info@ARKdynamics.org

Overview of the *MCDST Explorer v1.2*

- The *MCDST Explorer* provides a simulation of the growth of microalgae, in the form of a digital twin*, with which the user can gain an understanding of how a real culture system may function in response to changes to control variables.
- The user can alter a range of input variables, as they would when operating a real system, and observe the consequences in just a few minutes. This allows the user to rapidly explore different options both for the operation of the culture system but also for using microalgal strains of different physiological characteristics.
- Inputs are made by selecting between the options provided.
- Outputs are observed directly on the PC screen.

* a digital twin is a simulation model that provides a description of a recognisable reality with which the user can interface.

Operating Platform

- The *MCDST Explorer* operates under MS Windows, using a free-to-end-user application from Powersim.com (*Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit*).
- Both *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* and the *MCDST Explorer* operate (are installed) on the user's PC; they are not run off the cloud and no internet access is required.
- No special requirements are made of the PC itself, other than to note that older PCs will run the simulations more slowly, and PCs with multiple processor cores, advanced video graphics and RAM will run simulations faster. Even older PCs will provide answers within a minute or so.

QuickStart

- The *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* application works only on PCs operating *Microsoft Windows*.
- Do NOT install if you already have a *Powersim Studio* application installed !! – check the full instructions, below.
- Visit the *Powersim Studio* download site at <https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>
- Select the appropriate version of *Cockpit* between 64-bit and 32-bit (most PCs will be 64-bit).
- Follow the instructions provided by *Powersim* to install the software. (Accept default suggestions unless you have reasons to do otherwise.)
- To run the *Cockpit-enable Studio 10* model, first locate the file in your *MS Windows* file directory using *Explorer*.
- Locate the MCDST file : [ARK_MCDST_EXPv1_2_L.sip](#)
- The file should have the *Powersim Studio 10* logo associated with it - clicking on the file opens the file within the application.

Description

The *MCDST Explorer* describes the physiology and growth of microalgae growing in phototrophic mode. Simulations are for periods of up to 30d.

The simulation is of 3 culture systems allowing for a ready comparison between operational protocols (e.g., microalgal strains, nutrient or light regimes, harvesting regimes).

Culture system

The following details of the physical and chemical status of the culture system may be explored using the *MCDST Explorer*.

- Light at the surface of the culture, described as artificial with a square-wave light:dark cycle
- Culture system optical depth
- Harvesting options (frequency and proportion removed and replaced with fresh medium)
- Media configuration as dilutions of the classic *f/2* nutrient regime

Microalgal physiology

In the *MCDST Explorer*, microalgal configuration is limited to just the maximum growth rate. The model itself, however, describes growth with variable C:N:P:Chl stoichiometry, changing with nutrient supply and light. This variable stoichiometry is used to derive output data on dry weight and protein production.

The tool is available as a Powersim Studio Cockpit file: [ARKdynamics_MCDST_Explorer_L.sip](#)

Graphic User Interface

On loading the MCDST Explorer, the user is presented with the Home page.

Microalgae Culture Decision Support Tool (MCDST)
MCDST Explorer version v1.2

The Explorer version of the MCDST provides a simulation of the growth of microalgae, exploiting a simplified user interface for you to quickly and easily explore the implications of key bioreactor operations.

The MCDST allows you to manipulate three bioreactors, each of 1m³ volume, and run them simultaneously. This allows you to readily compare between your selected scenarios.

Details of microalgal physiology, of the growth media composition (set here as dilutions of the classic F-medium), and many other advanced options are available in full versions of the MCDST.

Follow these steps; you can switch between this **Home** window and the **Operations** window at any time:

- **Ctrl+R** to reset the model
- Change factors describing the bioreactor configuration, maximum microalgal growth rate and the harvesting protocol. Just click on your required selections. You can also enter financial information for an indication of the cost-benefit of your decisions.
- **Ctrl+Space** to run the model; use **F9** to re-scale plots during the simulation.
- Examine the results of your simulations for maximum harvest and crop characteristics, and minimum waste.

MCDST APPLICATIONS - microalgal laboratory research, commercial biomass production, aquaculture feedstock production, nutrient recovery from waste waters, etc.

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The product here provide only an example of what a MCDST can describe

The simulations also assume that the microalgae are only growing phototrophically and that the target product is in the algal biomass.

A full MCDST can describe mixotrophy, or indeed pure heterotrophy, and also report production of released chemicals.

Note that a full MCDST is a bespoke platform for your project!

Contact us to discuss your interests

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www.ARKdynamics.org

The *MCDST Explorer* application presents its functionalities via a single graphic user interface (GUI) page that is accessed via clicking the 'Operations' button.

Operations

Select **Fit** from the 'Zoom percentage' to see the entire display

PhotoBioreactor CONFIGURATION
Select required options

MAXIMUM MICROALGAL GROWTH RATE
Select maximum growth rate (d⁻¹)

HARVESTING
Select frequency (days) & % taken. The reactor is immediately refilled with fresh culture media for the next batch.

INSTRUCTIONS

Ctrl+R to reset the graphs. Parameterize each of the three 1m³ systems [1] [2] [3] for each variable, as required.

Ctrl+Space to run the simulation. **F9** to re-scale the graphs during the simulation.

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PBR functioning
Crop development & waste streams

Algal-Chl (gchl/m³)
Time (d)

Cumulative dry weight (g)
Time (d)

Waste
Cumulative NO₂-N used (mg)
Time (d)

Cumulative protein (g)
Time (d)

Cumulative fatty acids (gF)
Time (d)

Cumulative NO₂-N wasted (gN)
Time (d)

Cumulative DTP wasted (gP)
Time (d)

From here, selections are made by clicking on the options; these are triplicated because the simulation runs 3 scenarios simultaneously allowing the user to compare outcomes.

Operating the *MCDST Explorer*

The following gives a description of the configuration options.

Information is also provided throughout the interface by clicking on the information buttons:

Note that for each input, there are 3 options, one for each of the three systems. Likewise, the output plots show 3 curves, one for each system (noting that sometimes these may not all be visible if lines overlay each other).

Inputs

- **Optical depth:** three options are available (units of metres). The effective optical depth for a tubular or flat-plate reactor is affected by the geometry of the light source. If illuminated from both sides, it may be considered as the diameter of a tubular reactor.
- **PFD:** three options are available for the photon flux density ($\mu\text{mol photon m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Light is provided as a square-wave over the light-dark cycle. The value of PFD is that at the surface of the water in the reactor.
- **LD:** three options are available for the light:day ratio. A value of 1 sets continuous illumination.
- **Media:** three dilution options are available of the classic *f*-media. The most common version of this media is *f*/2, but here, *f*/4 and *f*/6 may be selected. *f*/2 contains 880 μM nitrate and 32 μM phosphate.
- **Microalgal maximum growth rate (UmRT):** three maximum growth rate (at the assumed fixed and optimal temperature) are offered. The unit is d^{-1} ; 0.35, 0.7 and 1.4 d^{-1} are, respectively, a doubling every 2, 1 or 0.5 d.
- **Harvesting frequency (har_f):** three options are available for the frequency of harvesting. These are 3, 5 or 10d.
- **Harvesting fraction (har_pc):** three options are available for the proportion of the system being harvested. These are 30, 60 or 90%. This proportion is removed at the frequency set by **har_f**, and is immediately replaced with fresh growth media, as set by **Media**. The non-harvested biomass acts as the inoculum for the next crop cycle.

Running the simulation

The simulation is started either by clicking the run-button in the control panel at the top of the screen, or simply using **Ctrl+space**.

To rescale graphs during the simulation, press **F9**.

Outputs

Outputs are provided via on-screen graphs. Data are all provided against time (in days).

Information is also provided for each graph by clicking on the information buttons:

- **Algal Chl:** this is shown for the 3 systems (gChl per 1m³). The values reflect changes in the biomass and photoacclimation (which varies with light received by the cells and their nutrient status). The shape of the plots reflect also the selected values of **har_f** and **har_pc**.
- **Cumulative dry weight:** this is shown for the 3 systems (g per 1m³). The display is of the cumulative harvested microalgal biomass; this is step-shaped in reflection of the selected value of **har_f**.
- **Cumulative protein:** this is shown for the 3 systems (g per 1m³). The display is of the cumulative harvested microalgal protein; this is step-shaped in reflection of the selected value of **har_f**.
- **Cumulative fatty acid:** this is shown for the 3 systems (g per 1m³). The display is of the cumulative harvested fatty acid (technically, storage C); this is step-shaped in reflection of the selected value of **har_f**.
- **Cumulative H2O used:** this is shown for the 3 systems as m³ assuming the reactor volume is 1m³. The display is of the cumulative usage. The plot is step-shaped in reflection of the selected value of **har_f**.
- **Cumulative NO₃⁻ wasted:** this is shown for the 3 systems as gN assuming the reactor volume is 1m³. The display is of the cumulative wastage, the balance of the nitrate provided in the media having been used by microalgal growth. The plot is step-shaped in reflection of the selected value of **har_f**.
- **Cumulative DIP wasted:** this is shown for the 3 systems as gP assuming the reactor volume is 1m³. The display is of the cumulative wastage, the balance of the phosphorous provided in the media having been used by microalgal growth. The plot is step-shaped in reflection of the selected value of **har_f**. Note that *f*-media is N-rich and thus often DIP is consumed while leaving an excess of NO₃⁻.

Saving the results

In the MCDST Explorer, results can only be saved by screen capture. It is advised to capture the entire screen so as to record the settings used for a given simulation.

Make sure that the entire *Operations* page is displayed; adjust the zoom magnification as required.

References

The following research was conducted using the same underlying description of algal physiology and PBR operations as within the MCDST.

- Flynn, K. J., Kenny, P., & Mitra, A. (2017). Minimising losses to predation during microalgae cultivation. *Journal of applied phycology*, 29(4), 1829-1840.
- Kenny, P., & Flynn, K. J. (2015). In silico optimization for production of biomass and biofuel feedstocks from microalgae. *Journal of applied phycology*, 27(1), 33-48.
- Kenny, P., & Flynn, K. J. (2016). Coupling a simple irradiance description to a mechanistic growth model to predict algal production in industrial-scale solar-powered photobioreactors. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 28(6), 3203-3212.
- Kenny, P., & Flynn, K. J. (2017). Physiology limits commercially viable photoautotrophic production of microalgal biofuels. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 29(6), 2713-2727.